

Compreendendo as percepções de executivos Brasileiros de empresas de software sobre os Fatores Críticos de Sucesso

Understanding the perceptions of Brazilian executives of software firms about Critical Success Factors

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1 Extended discussion about the achieved results based on the Conceptual Framework

The intent of CSFs is to identify the activities that are most important to managers to achieve an organization's mission. Based on this assumption and following the last stage of our methodological plan, we make available a validated and summarized version of our framework based on the insights achieved throughout the previous stages. Aiming to reach this objective, we picked up i) the CSFs defined as most important by each participant for each Thematic Group and ii) the CSFs with the highest priority averages. These results can be seen in Table 1 by the values in bold. The quantitative results have been congruent to the qualitative results obtained using Content Analysis, which endorses our findings. As one can notice in Figure 1, some Thematic Groups have only two CSFs (Innovation and Marketing) and others present four different CSFs (Operations).

Figure 1. Validated Framework.

Source: the authors.

We have derived from the initial Framework composed of 50 CSFs a final list of 17 CSFs (Figure 1), 3 of them suggested by the participants. Our aim is not to provide a “definitive” list of CSFs, but to make explicit a list of CSFs validated through the lens of both executives and theory, which may enlighten other organizations developing their competitive strategies. Next, we will discuss our framework's critical perspective according to the theory.

First, we noticed that Innovation Capability was the factor that reached the highest priority value in the AHP results. This conclusion seems relevant to our study since innovation capability is positively related to firm performance (Mone, McKinley, & Barker III, 1998). As stated by Rajapathirana and Hui (2017), firms that are not able to maintain satisfying levels of innovation capabilities through time tend to show weak performance in terms of competitiveness and economic results. In particular, Capaldo, Iandoli, Raffa, and Zollo (2003) point out that innovation is a necessary condition for increasing small software firms' competitiveness and ensuring their survival.

Another CSF raised by our validated framework was Scientific and Technical Research. A firm's ability to leverage both internal and external R&D activities has important implications for generating economic value from innovation and sustaining the firm's competitive advantage (Soh & Subramanian, 2014). In fact, rather than relying on internal and traditional structures of innovation, organizations are reported to increasingly engage in “Open Innovation”, by assuming that firms can and should use external ideas as well as internal ideas/paths to market, as they look to advance their technology (Chesbrough, 2006). According to Zhang, Yang, Qiu, Bao, and Li (2018), Open Innovation enhances firms' technological capabilities and overall competitiveness by combining internal and external ideas in innovative activities.

In terms of Operations, the software industry is unique, with gross margins as high as 80%, thus requiring proper attention to this issue (Bokhari, 2007). Li, Shang, and Slaughter (2010)'s studied the importance of operational capability for firm survival in the software industry. They highlight the importance of operational efficiency in helping the firm to persist, although managers of a software firm may focus on innovation. We have identified three

CSFs for the Operations factors, three of them related to the project/processes perspective (Proper management of knowledge areas, Clear and realistic specifications and Appropriate development processes/methodologies) and one related to the needs of internal IT customers. This attention of the interviewees to the project/processes perspective appeared to us of particular importance since it emphasizes an intent to work around the problem that software projects are often unable to be delivered on schedule, within budget or with the required functions. Illustrating this defiance, for instance, the 2015 Standish Group Chaos Report showed that only 29% of software projects succeeded (Hastie & Wojewoda, 2017). The drive to constantly improve the software development process and its quality is one of the major challenges faced by the Software Engineering research community (Sommerville, 2011). For instance, one particular issue that is widely investigated by this community is the study of agile methods, including its application on large-scale projects (Campanelli & Parreiras, 2015; Dingsøyr & Moe, 2014). On the other hand, we also identified the relevance of knowing the needs of internal IT customers. The literature usually addresses this factor and focuses on specific tools and approaches for improving developers' productivity (Meyer, Fritz, Murphy, & Zimmermann, 2014). Hence, we may assume that it is also relevant for software firms to invest in productivity-enhancing processes and tools to be operationally efficient (Li et al., 2010).

Some authors argue that a technology firm's culture tends to value technical knowledge more than marketing knowledge. Therefore, they are more likely to be managed by technology entrepreneurs than business-oriented entrepreneurs (Mohr, Sengupta, & Slater, 2010). However, software products are characterized by a high degree of complexity and intangibility, making the offering's support and service elements of paramount importance in the process of value creation for the customer (Ruokonen & Saarenketo, 2009). Grounded on this assumption, Helander and Ulkuniemi (2006) argue that software companies should develop a relational competency involving a comprehensive understanding of the technology as well as the customers. Our framework represents these findings through the following Marketing factors: Efficient sales force and Relationship with customers.

Regarding efficient sales force, Bokhari (2007) states that sales revenue for a software firm includes the income generated from software licenses, maintenance, and services. Moreover, for several types of software, especially for small software firms, as the most ones in the Brazilian market, a close relationship with the customer is crucial for their business (Alajoutsijärvi, Mannermaa, & Tikkanen, 2000). Reinforcing these arguments, Moen, Gavlen, and Endresen (2004) point out that executives of software companies have to manage the allocation of resources between expanding the network through the current relationships and focusing on establishing new relationships and customers.

The appropriate treatment of organizational issues has been recognized as playing a special role in the successful outcome of software projects (Koc, 2007). This argument seems reasonable since software development is an intellectual activity that requires creative problem-solving when applying innovation processes, methodologies, and tools (Sommerville, 2011). In this sense, the importance of non-technical factors in software development is underlined by Doherty and King (1998), which investigated that 90% of software projects failures can be assigned to non-technical (social, organizational etc.) factors. In addition, several authors have been studying how human and cooperative aspects impact software construction business at many levels and from many perspectives de Souza, Sharp, Singer, Cheng, and Venolia (2009). Our Organizational factors were 1) Human resources development and talent management, 2) Good leadership and top management commitment and 3) Customer involvement.

First, the success of a software project is highly sensitive to the capability and diversity of the assigned human resources (Tsai, Moskowitz, & Lee, 2003). However, people

management is not limited to assigning human resources to tasks in the development process and formalizing descriptions of the capabilities of both people, roles, and their interactions in the software process (Koc, 2007). Koc (2007) argues that firms have to enhance their human capital stock over time through training efforts directed at incremental problem-solving. On the one hand, the need to develop human resources is widely recognized, but, on the other hand, IT employee retention has also been a critical problem to IT organizations for several decades (Westlund & Hannon, 2008). Employees possessing technological skills in high-demand IT areas have shown more loyalty to their careers and personal development than to their organizations (Jackofsky, 1984). To overcome this problem, Tietjen and Myers (1998) argued that instilling satisfaction within workers is a crucial task of management since satisfaction creates confidence, loyalty, and ultimately improves quality in the employed output.

Moreover, researchers have conceptualized the Top Management Team (TMT) as the inner circle of executives who collectively formulate, articulate, and execute the strategic and tactical moves of the organization (Eisenhardt, Kahwajy, & Bourgeois III, 1997). Generally, the TMT includes leadership roles as the CEO and senior executives who hold positions at or above the level of vice president (CFO, COO, etc.) and report directly to the CEO. Carmeli, Schaubroeck, and Tishler (2011) examined how CEO empowering leadership shapes TMT behavioral integration and potency, enhancing firm performance. As concluded by Kirkman and Rosen (1999), teams headed by empowering leaders have become more proactive and develop a high level of job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

Over the past four decades, customer involvement in software development has been considered as one of the most crucial factors to achieve success (Ives & Olson, 1984). However, it has been shown that users are seldom involved, despite the common agreement that doing it would result in better and higher chances for project success (Kujala, Kauppinen, Lehtola, & Kojo, 2005). In fact, companies struggle to involve their customers and have a hard time selecting the right requirements from the enormous number of candidate requirements (Kabbedijk, Brinkkemper, Jansen, & van der Veldt, 2009). Corroborating this ongoing challenge, Bano and Zowghi (2013) conducted a Systematic Literature Review and concluded that user involvement is a multifaceted phenomenon that cannot be easily evaluated by a simple binary relationship with system success. Therefore, the presence of such a factor in our framework amongst the most important ones shows to be quite representative.

Three CSFs were identified to represent the External Factors: Political stability, Government support, and IT infrastructure. Existing research has shown that political instability had a negative effect on firms' performance (Hosny, 2017). In this sense, Brazil has been facing a serious crisis and political deterioration during the last years that directly affected its economic sectors, including the software industry. According to Wolf (2017), "Brazilian economy has suffered a huge recession, with real incomes per head down 9% between 2013 and 2016; growth is structurally too slow; the fiscal position is unsustainable, and a corruption scandal has engulfed the political elite and leading businessmen". More optimistically, in 2017, Celso Pansera (Chairman of the Softex Administration Board) stated that "with the economy leaving a strong crisis behind, the IT industry will surely gain prominence. Brazil is in a position to make a qualitative leap if it considers that the formatting of the new IT law is essential in this development process" (SOFTEX, 2016). To get a deep understanding about the public policy to software in Brazil, we suggest reading Pinheiro and Serafim (2015)'s work.

Complementing the need for Political stability, we have the Government support as another External CSF. The presence of both CSFs reflects a particular concern regarding the government role. Reaffirming this concern, Baer, Dávila, de Melo Modenesi, Fonseca, and

Kerstenetzky (2017) highlight that one major challenge to be faced by the Brazilian software firms is the access to financial resources to explore further a growth strategy based on mergers and acquisitions. According to them, the alignment between public policies and business strategies is essential for economic development. In terms of public initiatives to software production, the software industry is currently among the four areas prioritized by the industrial policy elaborated by the federal government. Fleury and Fleury (2007) pointed out two important actions made by the Brazilian federal government. The first was the development of the Brazilian Program of Quality and Productivity in Software (PBQP), created in 1993 by the Ministry of Science and Technology. The objective of the PBQP is to make Brazilian companies reach international standards of software quality and productivity. The second one was the creation of the National Export Software Program (Softex), in the early 1990s, aiming to stimulate the Brazilian industry in the realization of international business. Another important aspect to be highlighted is the current incubators' action in obtaining funding from government agencies such as Finep, CNPq, and BNDES, that is considered as a strategic incentive factor that supports high-tech entrepreneurship activities (Guimarães & Azambuja, 2010).

IT infrastructure is used in all e-business initiatives and may be defined as “the shared technology resources that provide the platform for the firm’s specific information system applications” (Laudon & Laudon, 2016). IT investment and its impact on organizational performance have been widely studied by a number of researchers (Barua, Kriebel, & Mukhopadhyay, 1991; Melville, Kraemer, & Gurbaxani, 2004). For instance, Law and Ngai (2007) found that IT infrastructure capabilities are positively related to business process improvements. Consistent with previous research, Xu, Zhang, and Barkhi (2010) mention that “the existing literature undoubtedly supported that IT infrastructure capabilities are critically linked to IT project success”. In addition, Devaraj and Kohli (2003) bring up an important discernment when they weigh in that performance benefits of IT infrastructure investment may not be fully realized unless IT applications are actually assimilated. In a government report concerned with the strategic formulation of IT public policies, there is a specific section devoted to discussing how imperative it is for the country to make the necessary investments in infrastructure (Gadelha et al., 2007). The authors claim that “the inexistence or low quality of this infrastructure will limit the diffusion of the use of ICT in the domestic market and will prevent any effort to export software services at competitive prices worldwide” (Gadelha et al., 2007).

Now, we have the last Thematic Group composed of the suggested factors made by the participants during the interviews, that is, Investing in Startups, Digital Marketing, and National Culture. It is worth noticing that all the participants did not evaluate these factors. They are all solely suggestions that we considered of particular importance since these CSFs were not previously identified during our literature review. Acquiring other startups, as clarified by Executive 1, is a factor that is closely related to the economic stage of the firm. In fact, this phenomenon has often been seen in the IT industry as, for example, through a large number of smaller startups that have been bought by big tech companies such as Google, Facebook, Amazon, and Apple. On the one hand, software startups are recognized by the development of innovative, software-intensive products within limited time and resources, searching for sustainable and scalable business models (Unterkalmsteiner et al., 2016). On the other hand, competition and market adversities pressure large corporations to seek alternative solutions to their processes, thus making it necessary to invest in innovative projects (Kon & Monteiro, 2014). This “demand and supply effect” ends up potentializing the purchase of startups by big companies to make them keep growing. Complementing with another perspective, Varrichio (2016) claims that “the open innovation strategy adopted by large Brazilian companies presents a new trend in Brazil: the approach with startups as a source of

inspiration, knowledge, and innovation”. Through an exploratory study, she noticed that a variety of models are currently available in Brazil, which ranges from financing to public calls to a long-term relationship as an accelerator for startups. She concluded that this movement can be considered positive because it encourages entrepreneurship and develops the innovation ecosystem, but it is still an unequal relationship on the different absorption capacity.

Moreover, as pointed out by Executive 1, Digital Marketing has a relevant role for engaging customers and partners. The Digital Marketing Institute defines digital marketing as “the use of digital technologies to create an integrated, targeted and measurable communication that helps acquire and retain customers while building deeper relationships with them” (Royle & Laing, 2014). In 2017, the Brazilian companies Rock Content and Resultados Digitais made available a report called TechTrends 2017 (TechTrends, 2017) about Brazilian technology firms' adoption of marketing digital tools. They accounted for 857 participants, and their insights are quite useful since it helps to analyze the benchmarks of the sector. Among the categories highlighted in the survey, the respondents' most adhesion was collaboration and productivity suites (Google Drive, Dropbox, Cubby, etc.): 99.3% of the companies interviewed use one or more of these platforms (TechTrends, 2017). However, in spite of the technology, digital marketing getting more competitive each year, we surprisingly identified a gap of papers specifically concerned with studying Digital Marketing in the context of Brazilian software development companies.

Last, we have the presence of National Culture, as suggested by Executive 3. Culture is “the collective programming of the mind which distinguishes the members of one human group from another” (Hofstede, 1980). Prior literature provides that national culture plays a significant role on firm performance (Griffin, Guedhami, Kwok, Li, & Shao, 2015), interpreting and responding to strategic issues (Schneider & De Meyer, 1991) and Corporate Social Performance (Ringov & Zollo, 2007), for instance. Furthermore, Biggart and Delbridge (2004) discuss that economic and business structures are culturally embedded, meaning that the structures vary in accordance with the society's culture. In this sense, Roth (1995) explains that a country's culture has long been identified as an environmental characteristic that influences consumer behavior. An illustrative example of this behavior was given by Executive 3 when he commented on the difficulty of making business at the beginning of the year given due to calendar issues. The cultural influences have usually been addressed in IT research by cross-cultural studies focused on offshore outsourcing and global information systems development, since it involves collaborations between two or more organizations, or between one organization and its subsidiaries, which occurs across national boundaries (Gurung & Prater, 2017; Huang & Trauth, 2007). Considering that Brazil is a spotlight for offshore and outsourcing software development, we assume this factor as meaningful for other companies.

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